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Developing a framework for assessing vulnerability of the houses in the context of landslide hazard: A study from Eastern Himalaya, India

Shivam Priyadarshi¹, Dr. Somnath Bera²

^{1,2} Department of Geography, School of Earth, Biological and Environmental Sciences,
Central University of South Bihar, Gaya, Bihar, India
somnath@cusb.ac.in, shivampriyadarshi@cusb.ac.in

The houses of the Himalayas are continuously damaged by the landslide that is emerging as a threatening issue against the security of the mountainous community. The assessment of housing vulnerability can serve as a potential tool for reducing landslide risk. However, a systematic framework for the assessment of the vulnerability of houses is limited in the literature. The present study develops a spatial framework for assessing the physical vulnerability of houses to landslide hazard scenarios. The methodology integrates two dimensions of vulnerability i.e., resistance capability index and exposure index. The study introduces a several sets of geomorphic conditions for evaluating the resistance capability index and adopts a spatial multi-criteria approach (Fuzzy-AHP) for assessing the vulnerability index. The method was applied to 332 houses surrounding the 13 active landslides of the Kalimpong region located in eastern Himalaya where data was collected using a GPS-based field survey and household interview. The result indicates that the vulnerability index varies at the micro-level in different scenarios due to a combination of resistance and exposure. Further, it is validated using R - the index method which denotes a positive association between partly damaged houses and the vulnerability index. The study will help towards building a safe and disaster-resilient society.

Keywords: Vulnerability index; Houses; Landslide; Geomorphic condition; Fuzzy-AHP; Damages